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Exploring the optical properties of MnO₂ nanoparticles doped PVP for optoelectronics devices

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Abstract

Numerous applications for optical technologies used the nanocomposites. The purpose of this work is to create novel kinds of polymer nanocomposites and analyze their optical characteristics. The polyvinyl pyrrolidone (PVP)/manganese oxide nanoparticle (MnO₂NPs) nanocomposites were created. Various content of PVA and MnO₂ NPs were fabricated. The optical characteristics of these nanocomposites were examined. The results demonstrate that the absorbance, coefficient of absorption, index of refractive, coefficient of extinction, dielectric constant and conductivity of PVP are raise with arise of the MnO₂NPs content. The transmittance and gap of energy are reduced with a rise of the MnO₂NPs content. The results illustrated the PVP/MnO₂nanostructures may be utilized in different photonics and optics fields.

Keywords: Nanocomposite; PVP; Optical devices; MnO₂; Optical properties

1. Introduction

Because of their numerous industrial applications, polymers are currently the focus of considerable scientific attention. The use of polymers in numerous scientific applications is necessary due to its fundamental properties, which include ease of production, low initial cost, durability, and remarkable processability [1]. Additionally, while choosing a polymer for a certain application, it is important to take into account its hydrophobic/hydrophilic balance, biocompatibility, optoelectronic behavior, chemical stability, and functionalities. The development of methods for using such materials while keeping the mentioned attributes and enhancing specific features like strength, modulus, fire performance, and heat resistance pose the biggest problems in the field of polymer research. In several cases, polymers can allow for easier shape and better manufacturing of composites [2]. According to reports, a polymer matrix can be used to create nanoparticles (NPs) since it possesses the characteristics of both the host polymer matrix and the visiting nanoparticles [3]. Dopants can be added to polymers to change their electrical and optical characteristics as needed. Additionally, these polymers have a reputation for being top-notch hosts. It is crucial to understand that the dopant alters the polymer's structure and therefore its properties because the field of polymer additives has received significant interest in today's materials research. Since the nature of the dopant and how it interacts with the polymer are what primarily determine how the characteristics of the polymer change, the dopant significantly improves the properties of the polymer when compared to pure polymers [4]. We can now produce novel nanoscale materials with unique electrical and optical properties that are very unique from those in their bulk state because to advancements in nanoscience and nanotechnology. The size-dependent characteristics of the nano materials were utilized in a variety of electrical and optical devices [5]. Synthetic polymers that are biodegradable, biocompatible, non-toxic, and simple to produce, like polyvinyl pyrrolidone (PVP), have many applications in biomedicine, engineering, and technology. When employing the solution casting method, this polymerase produces exceptionally optically clear films and is water-soluble. Since this polymer film has strong electrical insulation and a low permittivity, it is frequently used as a flexible dielectric material in the manufacture of organic thin-film transistors and optoelectronic devices. [6]. These hydrophilic polymers are

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frequently used as binders and capping agents in the creation of advanced composite materials because the hydroxyl (-OH) functional polar groups found in the chain backbone of PVP, from strong interactions with a variety of inorganic nanofillers [7]. A possible component for electrochemical lithium-ion batteries is manganese oxide (MnO_2). Through the easy insertion and extraction of lithium, high performance in electrochromic devices has also been improved. Additionally, catalysis employs thin layers of manganese oxide and as substrates in the growth of magnetic oxide perovskite materials [8]. The ability of manganese to modify its valence state underlies these uses for manganese oxide thin films. There are several valence states of manganese oxide, including MnO (Mn^{+2}), Mn_3O_4 ($\text{Mn}^{+2.67}$), Mn_2O_3 (Mn^{+3}), and MnO_2 (Mn^{+4}) [9]. The field of applicability is determined by the valence state. For instance, MnO_2 is a catalytic substance utilized in oxidation-reduction reactions as well as an electrode in lithium-ion batteries. Finally, Mn_3O_4 ($\text{Mn}^{+2.67}$) is a possibility for window applications due to its desirable electrochromic features, such as the ability to change optical transmittance in the visible spectrum in response to an applied voltage [10]. The composites materials have been extensively employed in the various approaches like aerospace, military equipment's, protective garments, sensors, safety, automotive, optical and electronics devices. On the other hand, these applications fields incessantly demand extra characteristics and purposes like flame retardation, elevated mechanical characteristics, chemical resistance, electrical conductivity, environmental stability, UV resistance, water repellency, radar absorption, magnetic field resistance, etc. [11-15]. In this work, we report to prepare and investigation of the optical characteristic of PVP/ MnO_2 nanocomposites to use in opto-electronics devices.

2. Experimental Method

The water-soluble synthetic polymers PVP (Mol. Wt. 20,000 g/mol, purity 99.99 percent, and melting point 230°C) can be acquired from (Central Drug House, Ltd, Company). The manganese oxide (MnO_2 NPs) were used as additive materials. PVP (100 wt. %) were mixed in 30 ml of deionized water with a magnetic stirring at 70 °C to obtain a more homogenous solution. MnO_2 NPs were added to the solution in varying weight percent (2, 4 and 6) wt. %. To create the (PVP/ MnO_2) nanocomposites, the casting technique was applied. The optical characteristics of PVP/ MnO_2 nanostructures films were tested using spectrophotometer (UV-1800A-Shimadzu).

The coefficient of absorption (α) is planned by [17]:

$$\alpha = 2.303 \left(\frac{A}{d} \right) \quad \dots\dots (1)$$

Which: A is the absorbance and d is the thickness. The gap of energy is given by [18]:

$$(\alpha h\nu)^{1/m} = C(h\nu - E_g) \quad \dots\dots\dots(2)$$

which C is constant, $h\nu$ is the photon energy, E_g is the gap of energy, $m = 2$ and 3 to indirect transition of allowed and forbidden.

The index of refractive (n) is defined by [19]:

$$n = \frac{1 + \sqrt{R}}{1 - \sqrt{R}} \quad \dots\dots\dots(3)$$

which R is the reflection. The coefficient of extinction (k) is determined by [20]:

$$k = \frac{\alpha\lambda}{4\pi} \quad \dots\dots\dots (4)$$

which λ is the wavelength. The dielectric constant parts: real (ϵ_1), and imaginary (ϵ_2) are given by [21]:

$$\epsilon_1 = n^2 - k^2 \quad \dots\dots\dots (5)$$

$$\epsilon_2 = 2nk \quad \dots\dots\dots(6)$$

The conductivity of optical (σ_{op}) is defined by [22].

$$\sigma_{op} = \frac{\alpha nc}{4\pi} \dots\dots (7)$$

3. Results and discussion

The variation of absorbance of PVP/MnO₂ nanostructures films are demonstrated in fig.(1). The absorbance intensity of PVP rises when the MnO₂NPs content rises, this is due to rise in the charge carriers density lead to increase in the absorbance values[23-25], while in fig.(2) the transmittance will reduce.

Figure 1 Absorption spectra of PVP/MnO₂ nanostructures films

Figure 2 Transmission spectra of PVP/MnO₂ nanostructures films

The coefficient of absorption (α) is useful to know the transition nature. The α values of PVP/MnO₂ nanostructures films as a function with wavelength are demonstrate in fig. (3). from this Figure, the α values $< 10^4 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ which indicates to the indirect transition. Figs. 4 and 5 illustrate the energies gaps values of PVP/MnO₂ nanostructures films of allowed and forbidden transitions. The E_g value reduces with rise in the MnO₂NPs content which relate to create of levels in the band gap lead to reduce in the E_g values [26-29].

Figs. (6,7) explain the extinction coefficient and refractive index of PVP/MnO₂ nanostructures films. The values of k and n of PVP rise when the MnO₂NPs content increases, these behaviors due to rise in the light scattering and absorbance [30,31].

Figure 3 Values of α for PVP/ MnO_2 nanostructures films

Figure 4 Gaps of energies values of PVP/ MnO_2 nanostructures of allowed transition

Figure 5 Gaps of energies values of PVP/ MnO_2 nanostructures of forbidden transition

Figure 6 Extinction coefficient performance of PVP/MnO₂ nanostructures films

Figure 7 Refractive index performance of PVP/MnO₂ nanostructures films

Figure 8 Variation of dielectric constant of real part of PVP/MnO₂ nanostructures

The dielectric constant of real and imaginary parts of PVP/MnO₂ nanostructures films are explain in figs (8,9). From these Figures, the values of ϵ_1 and ϵ_2 rises as the ratio of MnO₂NPs rises which relate to rise in the n and k values [32].

The variation of optical conductivity of PVP/MnO₂ nanostructures films with wavelength is represented in Fig.10. The σ_{op} value of PVP/MnO₂ nanostructures films rises with rise in the MnO₂NPs content and this behavior related to rise in the absorption and reduce in the energy gap [33,34].

Figure 9 Behaviour of dielectric constant of imaginary part of PVP/MnO₂ nanostructures

Figure 10 Influence of MnO₂NPs content on optical conductivity for PVP

4. Conclusion

The absorbance of PVP rises and the transmittance reduce with rise of the MnO₂NPs content. The PVP/MnO₂ nanocomposites have high absorbance in the UV-region. The gap of energy of polymer reduces with a rise of the MnO₂NPs content. Coefficient of absorption, index of refractive, coefficient of extinction, dielectric constant for real and imaginary parts and conductivity of PVP are raise with a rise of the MnO₂ NPs content. From this results illustrated the PVP/MnO₂ nanostructures may be utilized in different photonics and optics fields.

Compliance with ethical standards

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Disclosure of conflict of interest

No conflict of interest.

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